

When Spirituality Meets Creative Works and Design: A Theory on Trinity of Creative Practices

Anirban Chowdhury

School of Design, Graphic Era Hill University, Dehradun-248002, India.

Abstract: The nexus of faith, art, and design is an intriguing space where the concrete and the ethereal meet. This deep link explores the spiritual side of creativity and shows how transcendent experiences can influence the creative process. The incorporation of spiritual components lifts the work of artists, designers, and producers beyond the realms of aesthetics and functionality, as they set out on a journey of self-discovery and expression. This investigation spans a wide range of fields, including product design, architecture, and visual arts, encouraging a holistic approach that transcends simple craftsmanship to speak to the spirit of the maker and the observer. In this work, a theoretical framework was developed based on spirituality, humanity and peace and demonstrated its importance in design and creative practices; and, acceptance among creative community.

Practical Implications: The developed Trinity of Creative Practices (TCP) model has significant acceptance among design and creative professionals. This model might be beneficial for future designers to design products, services, interface or any other creative problem solving and will help to achieve sustainable development goals.

Keywords: Creativity; Design; Design Thinking; Problem Solving; Spiritual Practices; TCP model

1. Introduction

Spirituality in the context of art and design is fundamentally a wider sense of connectedness to something bigger than oneself than typical religious bounds. It explores the innate human curiosity to learn more about life, meaning, and the relationship between the material and the metaphysical (Birch & Sinclair, 2013; Walker, 2013; Walker, 2020). In order to understand the complex relationship between spirituality and creativity, this introduction will look at how spiritual ideas, mindfulness, and the pursuit of transcendence affect both the creative process and the products that come from it. The idea of spirituality is expressed in a variety of ways in creative works, with artists taking cues from a wide range of philosophical and cultural traditions. It can be seen in the meditative aspects of modern digital installations, the sacred geometry of architectural wonders, or the symbolism of ancient art. Using universal themes and archetypes gives artists' works a timeless quality and resonance that cuts across cultural barriers. They thereby extend an invitation to viewers to engage with a more fundamental and in-depth facet of the human experience. Spirituality has an impact on design, not just on aesthetic decisions but also on the fundamental qualities of spaces and goods. Adherents of spiritual concepts in design frequently give precedence to sustainability, ethical conduct, and the welfare of users, acknowledging the interdependence of all entities. This philosophy is demonstrated by the emergence of mindful design, which places equal emphasis on making objects that enhance people's lives individually and as a whole as well as on functionality. Spaces that arouse calm, carefully made items, and contemplative, participatory encounters are examples of how spirituality and design may coexist. When one examines the act of creation itself, the relationship between spirituality and creativity is much more evident. Many designers and artists characterize epiphanies as almost magical experiences that transcend the mundane and access a

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reservoir of creativity that surpasses personal capacity (Tan & Wong, 2012). In order to connect with this higher creative consciousness, creators frequently use rituals, mindfulness exercises, and meditation. The process of creating works that profoundly resonate is infused with a feeling of purpose and significance by this path of self-discovery and connection to something higher.

This investigation of the relationship between spirituality, artistic endeavors, and design is a call to investigate the process's capacity for transformation. It is a journey that invites participants to reflect on the meaning of their creative endeavors and the potential effects they may have on people as well as society at large, going beyond the obvious boundaries of aesthetic beauty or practical value. We hope to solve the enigmas surrounding the spiritual aspects of creativity through this investigation, revealing the manner in which these components enhance the human condition and add to the lasting heritage of artistic creations and design. This paper aims to develop a framework to demonstrate the importance of spirituality, humanity and peace for designing things and creative problem solving and its acceptance among design fraternity.

2. Generic Relationships Among Spirituality, Humanity and Peace

2.1. Relationship between Spirituality and Humanity

Spirituality and humanity have a close link that reflects the fundamental need for transcendence, meaning, and connection that characterizes the human experience. Spirituality, which is frequently an individual and reflective path, is essential in forming human morals, ethics, and a sense of direction. It includes investigating the metaphysical facets of life and inspiring people to look for meaning outside of the observable and material. Spirituality offers a framework for reflection and self-discovery through techniques like prayer, meditation, and mindfulness, encouraging a closer relationship with oneself, other people, and the cosmos. By addressing issues of morality, identity, and the interdependence of all living things, spirituality essentially enriches the human experience. The spirituality acts as a unifying force across cultural divides, fostering a common human understanding of the sanctity of life and the intrinsic worth of every person. Therefore, the central theme of our shared path toward a world that is more compassionate, meaningful, and interrelated is the relationship between spirituality and humanity.

2.2. Relationship between Spirituality and Peace

There is a strong correlation between spirituality and serenity, indicating a desire for human well-being, inner harmony, and connection. A sense of inner serenity and mindfulness are often fostered by spirituality, which acts as a guiding factor. Numerous spiritual traditions place a strong emphasis on virtues like forgiveness, compassion, and non-violence—values that serve as the cornerstone of both individual and societal peace. Spirituality can foster a profound understanding of connectivity that transcends boundaries and fosters harmony amongst many societies. People who practice spirituality that promotes reflection and empathy create a mentality that values harmony and respect for others, which makes the world a more peaceful place. In this sense, spirituality turns into a potent force that fosters social justice, collaboration, inner serenity, and peaceful outer surroundings. The connection between spirituality and peace highlights the possibility of common ideals and a group effort to create a world society that is more compassionate and harmonious.

2.3. Relationship between Humanity and Peace

The common goals of cultures around the world are fundamentally based on the relationship between humanity and peace. Fundamentally, peace is the result of people's shared desire for peaceful cohabitation. The pursuit of peace by humanity includes the settlement of disputes, the advancement of justice, and the creation of environments that support individual well-being. It displays an intrinsic understanding of how all individuals are connected to one another, despite differences in ideology, geography, and culture. In order to achieve peace, it is necessary to promote empathy, comprehension, and collaboration while acknowledging the intrinsic value and dignity of every individual. Humanity fosters peaceful society via valuing variety, defending human rights, and advancing equitable opportunities. Humanity and peace are mutually dependent since long-lasting peace can only be achieved via group efforts, compassion, and a shared dedication to creating an environment free from violence and fear.

3. Creative Practices and its Relationships with Spirituality, Humanity and Peace

3.1. Relationship between Spirituality and Design

There is more to the relationship between spirituality and design than just the outward beauty of material products; it involves a deeper connection between the human spirit and the creative process. In design, spirituality frequently entails investigating meaning, purpose, and how the built environment affects people's wellbeing. When spiritual principles are included into design, it can elicit feelings, give a feeling of community, and encourage peaceful coexistence with the environment (Joseph et al., 2017). Design choices can be influenced by spirituality, which can provide inspiration for aspects that align with cultural symbols, customs, and beliefs. The search for a spiritual connection during the creative process can produce more meaningful and compassionate results, whether in the fields of architecture, graphic design, or product design. This can create a sense of transcendence and elevate design beyond simple functionality to a realm that speaks to the human soul. The integration of spirituality and design is indicative of a comprehensive methodology that acknowledges the significant influence of the constructed surroundings on the human encounter.

3.2. Relationship between Humanity and Design

Humanity and design have a deep link because the human experience both fundamentally shapes and is shaped by design. Fundamentally, design is an expression of human requirements, goals, and wants. It entails a dynamic interaction between designers and users, whereby the former creates solutions that improve quality of life while the latter are inspired by the subtleties of human behavior, culture, and context. However, because they are the ones receiving the design, users also contribute through their feedback and interactions, which affects how iterative the design process is. Beyond simple utility, design resonates with the core of what it is to be human, embodying social dynamics, cultural values, and ethical considerations. Design is a fundamental aspect of the human experience, influencing everything from commonplace items to magnificent architectural constructions. It functions as a tool for people to communicate, express their identities, and navigate their surroundings. The mutually beneficial link that exists between humans and design highlights the significant influence that human-centered, intentional design can have in building a future that is more inclusive, sustainable, and sympathetic.

3.3. Relationship between Peace and Design

The deep relationship that exists between peace and design embodies the ability of design to promote togetherness, harmony, and understanding. When design is approached from a peaceful perspective, it transcends the purely practical and artistic components and can act as a catalyst for constructive societal change. Peaceful design in the built environment considers how areas might be welcoming, easily accessible, and supportive of wellbeing. The integration of sustainability, community involvement, and cultural sensitivity is crucial in urban planning, architecture, and product design as it helps create peaceful and interconnected spaces. Design may also be a tool for communication and conflict resolution, promoting discussion and tearing down boundaries with visual language. Essentially, a design approach that is focused on promoting peace is based on empathy, social responsibility, and a dedication to building spaces that help to create a world that is more harmonious and united. Thoughtful use of design principles with an emphasis on peace can motivate constructive transformation, influencing attitudes, behaviors, and the general well-being of society beyond tangible forms.

Figure 1. A model of Triangular Theory of Design.

4. Theory of Trinity of Creative Practices (TCP)

It's a triangular theory of design and creative practices (see, [Figure 1](#)). Spirituality (belief in God) leads to Humanity (empathy and thoughts for the betterment of human race/fulfilment of Sustainable Development Goals) leads to Peace leads to fruitful Creative Thinking/ Design/Planning leads to quality of life. In addition, peace means freedom from disturbance. If No peace (in presence of disturbance), no fruitful creative work/ planning/design. Peace comes from humanity and humanity comes from spirituality.

Another perspective is spirituality as a metaphor. Its metaphorical meaning is - your belief in creative practice and how you do practice it passionately, like a God believer do rituals in regular basis when praying/thinking about God. If you do creative practice passionately you do consider human beings and you do justice for quality of life through design intervention leads to peace.

If a design school/ studio has a peaceful work environment it might lead to better creative outcomes (Elsbach & Stigliani, 2018; Gómez-Rincón, 2023; Kumar & Sudarshan, 2022). The establishment of peace is possible through cultivation of empathy (as an essential component of humanity) among people, in the environment. The spiritual mindset is helping to build an empathetic environment and also helps to avoid disturbances through positive thinking/ emotional intelligence.

4.1. Methods

The developed TCP model was floated on LinkedIn and responses from the professional networks of the design and creative professionals was captured and analyzed using Chi-square test. The test statistics were then presented through donuts plot.

4.2. Results and Discussion

The TCP model has been viewed and discussed in professional platform (LinkedIn) over 3 days. Many creative professionals viewed (N=3201) the TCP model floated online across the globe. The people viewed the shared TCP model from top five cities like Delhi (8.1%), Pune (7.3%), Bengaluru (6.6%), Mumbai (6.4%) and Kolkata (1.9%) (see, [Figure 2](#)). These viewers were having various job titles such as professors, user experience designers, lecturers, product designers, research assistants (see [Figure 3](#)). Among all reactions 13 comments and 1 repost were noted. A total of 60 reactions were recorded in LinkedIn within 3 days. These 60 reactions are composed of like, support, celebrate, love and insightful. Significantly a greater number of design professionals liked (90%) the TCP concept [$\chi^2(4) = 184.000, p = 0.0001$]. The percentage of other types of responses were presented in [Figure 4](#).

Figure 2. Location Wise Demographics of Unique Viewers.

Top demographics of unique viewers ⓘ

Figure 3. Job Role Wise Demographics of Unique Viewers.

Figure 4. Responses of Viewers for The Framework of Trinity of Creative Practices (TCP).

Figure 5. Dustbin in Children’s Park Inspired from the Hippopotamus.

5. Conclusion

As per the Indian mythology, Pashupati Nath (Lord Shiva) says to love animals, it will help humanity by balancing the natural ecosystems. However, sometimes we ask our kids to put wastes in the Dustbins which are designed in the form of animals (animacy), e.g. design inspired from the form of monkey, hippopotamus (see **Figure 5**), etc.; and such Dustbins are often situated in children's parks. Eventually, kids are learning wrong things and it might happen that out of this wrong learning kids might try to feed plastics or any other wastes to animals when visiting a zoo. As a consequence, animals might die or be killed by an innocent kid.

Now the question is - Is this kind of design of Dustbins are good? Who is responsible? The kid or the designer/creative professional?

That's why designers need to understand spiritual, humanitarian and peace aspects of their creative works (Humbukers, 2021). The developed Trinity of Creative Practices (TCP) model has significant acceptance among design and creative professionals. This model might be beneficial for future designers to design products, services, interface or any other creative problem solving and will help to achieve sustainable development goals.

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